

INTEGRATION OF PUBLIC AND PRIVATE HEALTH CARE DATA WITH MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract

The integration of data and machine learning has been proven to be very useful. Both present and future applications would enhance data analytics in the healthcare sector and other sectors of the economy. Many institutions and organizations, including governments of nations, invest heavily in data analytics for effective decision-making. The integration of both public and private healthcare data will improve the quality of the healthcare system, reduce the cost of treatment, and make public access to healthcare data available. This paper explores the integration of public and private health care data with machine learning, analyzing the concept of data integration, the usage of machine language, machine learning, and data integration connection, the challenges of data integration, the needs of the health care system, and recommendations for the system in developing nations as well as other countries health care system.

Keywords: Datasets, Healthcare, Public, Private, Integration, Machine Learning

Introduction

Nations and organizations all over the world are spending several millions of dollars to integrate data for effective business intelligence and adequate decision-making at a time when budgets are severely strained and every dime counts (Giordano, 2011). Well-resourced, the sometimes fragmented private healthcare sector can learn from the integration efforts of the public health

sector. In academic and public functional hospitals and health centers, medical teams often come together to deliberate on a joint treatment plan for patients, but in the private sector, physicians seldom work in integrative teams (Malan, 2017). Lack of information sharing and communication between the public and private sector results in low-quality care and higher cost of treatment as a result of waste due to the findings done many times by various physicians. Ideally, an integrated database system will narrow the difference between the rich private sector and the under-funded public sector for easy access by the citizens making it publicly available. Stakeholders in the public healthcare sector and government and those in the private healthcare industry must see the benefit of working closely together in order to integrate public and private healthcare data.

The basis of the integration is Big data. According to Onukwugha (2016), Big data is a large amount of information that needs modern technologies for storage, capture, or analysis due to the amount of information, the speed of production, and its content. Omoyiola (2022) explained it as an outburst in the volume and quality of available and applicable data as a result of modern and outstanding breakthroughs in data analytics. Integrating data has to do with the business and technical processes used to integrate data from various means to give a unified, single view of the data. Integrating big data into healthcare will save lives and improve healthcare (Heath, 2014). Without a doubt, in this era of machine learning, data integration plays an important part in the digital revolution of any organization in healthcare.

Aims and Objectives of the Healthcare System

The main aim of a healthcare system of a nation is to provide the citizens with healthcare services when they need them and to provide healthcare services that are affordable and meet quality standards. The healthcare sector has not fully seized the potential benefits associated with big data analytics (Wang, Kung, & Byrd, 2018). Data integration in the healthcare sector will

stabilize medical resources, enhance diagnosis and treatment, and reduce the cost of patient expenditure on healthcare (Zhan & Zhang, 2014). Data integration combines data from different sources, which is essential in today's data-driven economy to enable business competitiveness, customer satisfaction, and operations, which rely on integrating various data sets. As an increasing number of firms adopt digital transformation utilizing the integration of data, the ability to access and combine data becomes critical. Information from an integrated database may be used for local assessments or evaluations of private and public health facilities in the State, as well as in medical systems, like for certain inpatient hospital occurrences or outpatient situations in the State (WHO, 2018). The data from the integrated database could also be used regionally or nationally to assess or evaluate performance within or across healthcare systems. Also, since the comparison is inevitable, the database could be a good source to gather information for comparing healthcare services across federal borders to measure the differences in disease control and healthcare in different nations.

As an important element of national security, public and private healthcare centers do not just offer enough and timely healthcare services but also control and keep track of disease epidemics. The healthcare system of developing nations needs more medical professionals year after year, hence the need to tackle the problem. This research aims to provide integrated database system solutions for both private and public healthcare service delivery systems in developing nations and to offer practicable recommendations for the failing condition of the healthcare system caused by the lack of efficient integrated database systems in the nations. An up-to-date recommendation for a healthcare delivery system to review the dynamics of the integrated database system is discussed with respect to medical intelligence/surveillance in developing nations like Nigeria (Menizebeya, 2011).

There has been an increase in the preference for electronic data over paper records since 1980, when NHS began to gather data on all patient admissions in the United States as per

Hospital Episode Statistics. Information was traditionally stored by NHS as anonymous data eliminating information on prescription drugs and test results from the record. This gave significant gaps in the existing records, thus distorting the complete picture of a patient's health data. In order to anonymize data in the 1990s, the National Health Scheme (NHS) identification number was developed. Data anonymization was further developed by NHS on medical records, which allows for linking two records holding patients' details in different locations. The information which was added to a national database holds the demographic data on every single citizen, such as their personal information and registered General Practitioners. The national database also includes the summary of clinical conditions and major treatments of the individual to provide anonymous data for both public health and health services research.

The NHS infrastructure called the National Program for IT (NPfIT), was developed in 2000 as a single repository for healthcare data in England to allow medical information to be utilized for academic and research works. The NHS national program for IT (NPfIT) initiated by NHS did not gain buy-in from key stakeholders until stakeholders were meaningfully engaged. NHS recommended that key stakeholders should be engaged, their needs should be met, and they should present the norms and values on the privacy of healthcare data. The integration of public organizations with private mediation is very key.

Big data is important to NHS continuity, the healthcare of patients, and the integration of the practices of the private sector and the public sector database in order to stimulate innovation in patient privacy. The patients' privacy and data protection act should be imposed to determine statutory conditions on data processing and to balance the need for organizations to collect data for defined purposes against individual rights. Acts like the Patient Privacy and the Data Protection Act of 1998 impose explicit statutory conditions on the processing of data and aim to balance the legitimate need of firms to gather data for defined purposes against the individuals'

right to respect the privacy of their personal details (Presser, Hruskova, Rowbottom, & Kancir, 2015).

Developing Nations' healthcare systems needs

There is a need for reforms in the health care system of developing nations such as Nigeria. Access to health, according to Menizibeya (2011), is only 43.3%. This inadequacy is attributed to the peculiar demographics of a developing nation like Nigeria, which has more than half of the populace inhabiting the rural regions and less than half inhabiting the urban cities. More than half of the health services are provided by private care facilities, while only 30% are owned by the government. More than half of the populace doesn't have the money for good healthcare. Akande (2004) opined that the lacking a referral system between the different levels of healthcare affects the management of the healthcare system. There should be solutions at the primary healthcare level. There should be access to quality health. The NHIS must review the present healthcare and improve it. The digital transformation of the Healthcare system of developing nations will make them world-class.

Concept of Data Integration

Data integration is the integration of data from varied sources, offering the end-user an integrated perspective of the data. The design of data integration systems for modern-day applications is very important. It could have some interesting issues from a theoretical point of view (Lenzerini, 2007). The importance of data integration is seen in large enterprises with the multitude of data sources used in mega scientific works where datasets are independently produced by several researchers for better collaboration among government agencies, each with their own data sources to offer good search quality on the world wide web across millions of structured data sources (Halevy, Rajaraman, & Ordille, 2006). Healthcare data integration is defined as the organization and management of healthcare services so that citizens can receive

the healthcare they require with user-friendly methods, get their needs met, and get value for their money (Malan, 2017). Developing nations need this integrated healthcare for better results. The State healthcare delivery systems desperately need an integrated database management system to improve healthcare services.

An integrated database management system is essential for data generation and data management in firms. Health system databases serve important roles in healthcare, which include administration, patient care, and education and research. The standard and scope of data collected into an existing database vary tremendously between databases, institutions, and national boundaries. Integrated health database means different things to different people, and it is important to clearly state what the term means. Integrated database for healthcare service delivery is the organization and management of healthcare services data so that people access needed data anytime, in ways that are user-friendly, to get a desired outcome and offer value for money (Malan 2017). The State healthcare delivery system could be advanced substantially by the development of integrated, comprehensive, and accurate databases. These healthcare databases should be created for the purpose of assessing the quality of healthcare service delivery, often for a specific disease or within a specific healthcare delivery system in both private and public healthcare facilities. (Greg, 2008). Prudence and pragmatism should rule the day when considering real-time data integration (Giordano, 2011).

A healthcare database is an essential component in understanding and improving critical care worldwide. The usage includes novel research investigations for important areas in healthcare. For example, the application of the Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation (APACHE) database allows the examination of the relationship between hospital data and outcomes of mechanically ventilated patients (Kahn, Goss, Heagerty, Kramer, O'Brien, & Rubenfeld, 2006). This database, APACHE, includes detailed information on clinical physiology and laboratory abnormalities. Developing nations as critical care communities desperately need

well-conceived, comprehensive and accurately collected healthcare databases for both private and public healthcare facilities. It is, therefore, important to create a comprehensive database for purposes inclusive of healthcare quality, research, and education (Greg, 2008).

Developing nations' healthcare system needs the integration of adequate medical intelligence and surveillance systems in the State to reduce quacks from operating and preventing health fraud. The government should also address the key problems of poverty and illiteracy, which are twin brothers promoting the practice and acceptance of medical quackery. This statement suggests that the promotion of quackery involves deliberate deception. Health fraud is the promotion, for profit, of a false/unproven medical remedy (FDA, 2009). Our healthcare system will continue to be poorly developed if no effective and functional integrated database system for healthcare service delivery is put in place.

Challenges of data integration:

The projects on better data integration are affected by poor availability of accurate and reliable standards and data (for example, data on morbidity, economy, society/community and primary care, and social health insurance) and data collection techniques. There is diversity in the approach nations integrate data from varied sources as a result of variations in legislative regulations and personal identifiers. (NITDA, 2019)

A major hazard to data integration is the electronic medical record (EMR) data collection without patients' authorization. The electronic health record (EHR) is a major component of medical informatics used in developed nations to improve healthcare services. Non-uniform standard information and hospitals' unwillingness to share data are other significant obstacles to integration (Akanbi, et al. 2012). The unsustainability of public finance investment and friction caused by administrative decentralization are also hindrances to data integration. In other to solve these problems, firstly, to adopt a protocol for multi-stakeholder participation in data

collection. Secondly, there should be co-establishment information standards of administrative authorities and a data audit mechanism, and finally, propose measures to expand data integration to multiply effectiveness and adopt the Public-Private Partnerships model (Wang, 2019). EMR, as an important source for big data analysis, is used beyond the traditional use in disease treatment to drive decision-making in public health programs, identify risk factors for infectious diseases, enhance continuity care between institutions of medical learning, improve quality of healthcare delivery, facilitate medical research, catalyzes epidemiological surveillance, and support clinical decisions. The integration of healthcare data from numerous providers within the country has become a critical necessity. Countries like Germany, the USA, The UK, and others have made great efforts to achieve this task. Unfortunately, in developing nations, if a patient changes hospitals, the recipient doctor cannot access all the records from previous health facilities visited. The major problem lies in the lack of data integration. China's State Council in June 2016, in a bid to promote data integration and utilization, issued Opinions on Promoting and Regulating the Development of Big Data Applications in Healthcare (Wang, 2019). This aims to enable the construction of a unified population healthcare information platform. Electronic medical records could be taken as the core resource building for the platform of healthcare big data resources to promote resource sharing (Gao, Xu, Sorwar, and Croll, 2013).

Figure 1. Data collector's relationship. Integration of EMR data.

The integration of EMR data from several hospitals, clinics, and healthcare centers is a precondition for big data analysis. Both developed and developing countries are putting great efforts into data integration. Data sharing and transparency enable valuable results for managing patient care and encourage innovation in both public and private health institutions. The creation of a national database and data-sharing platform could involve various decision-makers and participants. To make sure there is control and transparency of the patients' data, all patients must be clearly informed on the benefits and risks of handling their personal data and its practicable usage. Also, hospitals' rights to control, use, and benefits of patient medical data should be acknowledged, and the responsibility of protecting the privacy and precision of their patients' records should be confirmed. There are abundant hospital data but little outpatient services data, particularly from the private segment. There are issues relating to poor definitions and a lack of standards for data collection and meta-data description. There is a need for an integrated method for the unification of classifications and codebooks or code converters for various parallel coding systems, particularly in data generation.

Data integrated from various database systems across the nations include data on mortality, inpatient data, cancer registry, and medical prescription. Data integrated with data from primary healthcare, population health survey, mental hospital inpatient, and long-term care are not as prevalent. While in some countries linking is made possible with the use of personal identifiers, for example, data on mortality from the cancer registers or from the HIV aids registers (Wang, 2019).

Using Machine Language

In the dispensation of digital transformation technologies like artificial intelligence and machine learning, data integration plays an important part in the digital revolution of any organization in

any sector. As data volume and variety increase, so is machine learning accepted. The exponential increase in computational power has also enhanced the efficiency of machine learning-based algorithms and has made machine learning a practical analytical tool.

The conventional algorithms (that involve a man directly coding an algorithm), in comparison to machine learning-based techniques, are more refined for the reason that they learn based on actual training data. Furthermore, the flexibility in machine learning-based approaches is the reason that the techniques are adaptable to changes via lessons learned from feedback. Thus, implementing machine learning is an effective replacement for direct programming. For example, machine learning-based algorithms for search-result ranking have incorporated explicitly programmed yet successful algorithms like the page rank algorithm. Machines or automated software are now trusted even though they are not fully comprehended, as seen by successful route-planning recommendation systems like Waze and Google Maps. The usage of machine learning algorithms on metadata, social context, and operational characteristics is for the identification of clean, accurate, and relevant data for various analytics exercises. For example, the clustering algorithms could be used for data catalogs, grouping similar data sets. In comparison, integrative filtering algorithms can be utilized to recommend the more useful ones in each context.

The Machine Learning and Data Integration Connection

Firms utilize data from the highest feasible sources so that the implementation of their digital transformation technologies, such as machine learning, can be efficient and the analysis can be detailed. An algorithm of machine learning is good if the data which trained it is good.

Organizations find it difficult to explain dark data and make use of it.

According to Dong and Rekatsins (2018), data integration systems rising to this challenge of dark data have resorted to an emergence of various data catalogs and data lake management

outputs. These outputs are like Google for data and provide a simple search-based interface to search and explore the data in an organization, at the same time respecting and honoring existing access control mechanisms. Increasingly, data integration systems are using machine learning-based methods to look for and display the utilizable data in the pool of abundant dark data to improve analytics (Kumar et al., 2017). Metadata, with the help of machine learning, is gaining a stronger emphasis in data integration. Examples include the usage of machine learning in schema inference, common value patterns, and data distributions. Most machine learning algorithms are utilized in metadata, operational characteristics, and social contexts for the identification of precise, relevant, and pure data for analytic exercises.

In a conceptual organization of machine learning methods for data integration, early integration starts with transforming datasets into a graphical representation or unified feature table utilized as an input to a machine learning approach. The method uses all kinds of dependence between the features of machine learning depending on individual datasets that do not fail prior to analysis. The quick integration methods depend on approaches for automatic feature learning in dimensionality reduction and representation learning to project high-dimensional datasets which are raw to a low-dimensional vector space integrating the low-dimensional representations through concatenation or other simple aggregation methods (Zitnik et al., 2018).

During the late integration, a first-level model is independently built for each dataset or data type. These first-level models are then integrated by training a second-level model which utilizes the first-level model predictions as features or via a meta-predictor that uses a major vote or integrates prediction weights of the first-level models. The intermediate integration with multiple kernels learning collective matrix factorization or deep neural network learns a joint representation of many datasets depending on algorithms that explicitly resolve the multiplicity of datasets and integrate them via the joint model interference. It is important to note that an intermediate data integration method does not integrate input data nor create a different model

for each dataset. The intermediate integration method aims at preserving the structure of data and only merges them during the analysis stage. This intermediate integration approach could result in higher performance; however, it needs the creation of another algorithm and may not be used with off-the-shelf software tools (Zitlink et al., 2018). Lastly, data integration methods can produce various kinds of prediction products, like techniques for the analysis of a dataset.

Recommendations

So many flaws in the health care delivery system could be averted through adequate management information system (MIS), which ought to be the initial action point in building and integrating the health care system in developing nations. However, the list of barriers includes the pattern of leadership, infrastructures, manpower shortage, adequate training, standardized diagnostic instruments, and others.

In other to account for the modern-era needs of the citizens of developing nations, the health care delivery system must adequately be integrated to meet the following functions:

- 1) Achieving success in healthcare delivery with good leadership and a well-integrated database system with medical intelligence managed by IT experts.
- 2) Relevant agencies need to strengthen professional standards and regulations in the country.
- 3) Accurately recording data, updating, and tracking data on the database efficiently and on a regular basis could enable private healthcare facilities and public healthcare facilities to address quackery and health fraud challenges.
- 4) By collecting notes and updated data, private and public health facilities could use the information in the database to meet their targets in a methodical manner and improve their facilities strategically.

5) By adopting the 2012 Health and Social Care Act. This explores the power struggles in the issues regarding care data and outlines the tensions among various stakeholders, General Practitioners, patients, the Health and Social Care Information Centre, government, privacy experts, and data purchasers

Conclusion

The use of integrated database management systems for both private and public health care service delivery will allow for the relationship within health facilities in the State. The system also will allow newer and better updates. A useful and productive integrated database management system allows data managers to enter new data, update the present data and delete the data not required. This system will enter names and medical activities of all private and public health facilities in each State, both licensed and non-licensed facility records and update all required information and allow citizens to access and track all health facilities and licensed healthcare professionals in the States.

Security is an important part of a database management system because data must be extremely accurate, reliable, secure, and preserved at all costs. A data breach could lead to loss of data. Similarly, sensitive data should be guarded against theft, fire, unintentional risks, and human error (Omoyiola, 2020). According to the Global World Health Alliance (WHO, 2018), The absence of a common data collection system in collecting data results in poor public and private sector coordination which means that various stakeholders will get fragmented information.

The integration of both private and public healthcare databases would bridge the gap between public and private healthcare facilities in the States. Some private facilities have costly diagnostic machines and theatres that are seldom used in the evening (Malan, 2017). They have excellent EHR systems that the public sector may gain from. This could be political and not

technological, as Broomberg (2017) stated. The main challenge in this program will be the cooperation of leaders in government and private healthcare sector stakeholders to work more closely together, as this has proved difficult over the years (Malan, 2017). Secondly, nations have varying legislative frameworks for the collection of data, the usage of personal information, and the integration of data. There are legal regulations in integrating personal information, like data on health and social status and statistics on mortality. Thirdly on technical ICT infrastructure, there may challenge with the integration of health information systems, such as the migration of data from paper format to electronic formats. There may also be other technical ICT infrastructure challenges, such as access and connectivity, like in rural regions.

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